

Survey on Reactions to the Coronavirus (COVID-19)

Informed Consent

Hello, we are conducting a survey about the COVID-19 anxiety Scale. We will appreciate it if you take about 5 mins off of your time to assist complete this survey for us. All the information we obtain will remain strictly confidential in our database. If you partake in this survey, you are assisting to stop the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic among the residents worldwide.

Thank you.

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* Required

Sociodemographic

Gender *

Male

Female

Age *

Your answer

What is your level of Study *

- Low
- Medium
- Professional

Are you married *

- Yes
- No
- Other:

What is your Religion? *

Your answer

People's characteristics on Fear of COVID-19 Scale

Note that: 1 (Strongly Agree), 2 (Agree), 3 (Strongly Disagree), and 4 (Disagree).

I am most afraid of coronavirus-19 *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

It makes me uncomfortable to think about coronavirus-19 *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

My hands become clammy when I think about coronavirus-19 *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I am afraid of losing my life because of coronavirus-19 *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

When watching news and stories about coronavirus-19 on social media, I become nervous or anxious *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

I cannot sleep because I'm worried about getting coronavirus-19 *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

My heart races or palpitates when I think about getting coronavirus-19 *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Are some of your relatives infected with COVID-19? *

- Yes
- No

Perception

How do you rate the danger of COVID-19 disease *

1 2 3 4 5

It has affected me a lot Not affected me at

How do I consider my overall mental health status before COVID-19 *

1 2 3 4 5

It has affected me a lot Not affected me at

COVID-19 information search frequency level *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

To what extent do you think that the number of fake news (not confirmed or verified by any official organizations such as WHO, Ministry of Health, and so forth) is overwhelming? *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

To what extent do you think that the number of official news (confirmed or verified by any official organizations such as WHO, Ministry of Health, and so forth) is overwhelming? *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

Obsession with COVID-19 Scale (OCS)

How often have you experienced the following activities over the last 2 weeks?

I had disturbing thoughts that I may have caught the coronavirus *

- Not at all
- Rare, less than a day or two
- Several days
- More than 7 days
- Nearly every day over the last 2 weeks

I had disturbing thoughts that certain people I saw may have the coronavirus *

- Not at all
- Rare, less than a day or two
- Several days
- More than 7 days
- Nearly every day over the last 2 weeks

I could not stop thinking about the coronavirus *

- Not at all
- Rare, less than a day or two
- Several days
- More than 7 days
- Nearly every day over the last 2 weeks

I dreamed about the coronavirus *

- Not at all
- Rare, less than a day or two
- Several days
- More than 7 days
- Nearly every day over the last 2 weeks

UCLA Loneliness Scale (RULS-6)

How much of the time do you feel the following

Note that: 4 (often), 3 (sometime), 2 (rarely), and 1 (never).

I lack companionship *

- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1

I do feel alone *

- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1

I am no longer close to anyone *

- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1

I feel left out *

- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1

No one really knows me well *

- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1

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